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Influence of Teacher Demonstration Video on Polytechnic Students' Achievement in Shorthand

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ABSTRACT

This study is quasi-experimental research which investigated the influence of teacher demonstration videos on polytechnic students' achievement in shorthand. Sixty polytechnic students were randomly assigned to either a (experimental group (n = 30) and control group (n = 30) through a simple random sampling technique. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics and an independent-samples t-test. Results showed that students in the experimental group significantly achieved higher than those in the control group at post-test. Some of the recommendations of this study suggested that teacher demonstration videos are effective supplement to traditional shorthand instruction and should be only used when found suitable enough to achieve instructional objectives.

Keywords: teacher demonstration videos, students' achievement, shorthand

INTRODUCTION

Studying Shorthand to students of office technology and management department is a paramount thing that cannot be skipped by any office technology and management (OTM) student. Shorthand is a vital component in OTM curriculum that strengthens and model students' vocabulary needed for office correspondence formation and meticulous speech recording (Oden, 2018). Shorthand is the art of representing speech sounds by written signs. Shorthand provides distinctive signs to distinctive sounds and corresponding similar signs to every similar sound. These techniques made it possible for secretaries and other Shorthand users to write at great speed, speeches made by speakers at meetings, conferences, and record executive instructions in the office (Okoro, 2018). Since Shorthand is based on speech sounds, Shorthand writers are called "sound writers". The employment of the use of signs to meticulously represent speech sounds made Shorthand writers, sign writers.

Appropriate use of signs for representation of speech sounds require efficient learning of such signs' writing and sounds' listening. A conventional classroom instruction depends on the teachers' voice and audio recording devices to teach learners the art of sound listening; then the Chalk and white boards are utilized for teaching the art of writing Shorthand signs (Okoro, 2018). For personalized or individual studies at home, Shorthand students make use of audio records from audio tapes and other audio recording devices. The audio tapes contain records of dictated matters for students to listen to and write out the drills. But students learning through this medium only have the opportunity to listen to audio instructions as the physical presence of teacher is missed. This feature can be remediated by use of relevant instructional media that may provide the learner with the visual aspects of the instructional content.

Recent developments in instructional media prompt the need for teachers to explore the use of various technologies that would leverage the tasks of teaching and learning on various subjects. Efficient selection and utilization of these technologies by teachers depends on the teachers' keen attention to simplicity, accessibility, and ease of maintaining the technologies and the achievement of teaching and learning objectives (Bakla, 2022). One of the instructional technologies found in modern classrooms today, are videos.

Video instructions portray both audio and visual aspects of instructions for students to both see and hear about instructional contents delivered by teachers. Video succeeds in concretizing the abstract aspects of the instructional contents to students making it possible for students to learn about experiences that are otherwise impossible to be seen or learnt physically by the students (Bakla, 2022). Video also allows for follow-up drills by students as students have the opportunity to use them again and again until a particular knowledge of interest is gained. Video instructions also enable teachers to reach out to a wider community or large class size of students that would not have been possible in the physical classroom setting (Sani, 2020).

The use of technology has made it possible for teachers to create instructional videos in a number of ways. Teachers could now recreate exiting video contents from the videos found on the online sources such as Tedex, Itunes, Youtube-edu; They could also adopt the use of already prepared educational videos found on the achieves of modern and online libraries for their instructional purposes. Consequently, teachers could also create their own demonstration videos for their instructional delivery (Chontos, 2024). Teacher demonstration videos are form of videos made by teachers performing demonstrations of instructional concepts for learners on various topics and subjects (Chontos, 2024). The use of these videos on Shorthand instructions may enable Shorthand students have access to teachers' demonstration of how Shorthand signs are made while the engaged into individual or personalized learning unlike the audio instruction that only allows them to hear the instructors' voices. This paper therefore tends to investigate the Influence of Teacher Demonstration Video on Polytechnic Students' Achievement in Shorthand

Literature Review

A number of literatures were conducted on instructional video and multimedia learning. Mayer (2009) for instance introduced foundational principles of multimedia learning. The principles guided modern instructional video design to enhance cognitive processing and learner engagement emphasizing how words and pictures can be combined to foster deeper understanding. The book outlines principles such as the modality principle (where audio narration was paired with visuals), segmenting principle (where information was presented in manageable parts), and signaling principle (where cues were used to highlight key information). Another study relating to media production is the study of Guo *et al.* (2014) who analyzed large-scale MOOC data to identify production factors influencing student engagement. The study found that shorter videos (under between six minutes length), videos using conversational tone, and have instructor presence in them significantly improved viewer retention and learning outcomes. The study reported that authentic, low-production videos were more effective than the highly polished videos, which shaped best practices for online course design. These studies are significant to this research work as they give guides on how instructional videos should be made.

Kay (2012) conducted a comprehensive review of literature on video podcasts and lecture capture technologies in education. The study reported an increased flexibility, and improved students' comprehension on self-paced learning although it reduced classroom interaction. Kay recommended video podcasts as valuable supplements for blended and online learning environments. Literature on the influence of instructor on instructional videos was conducted by Beege *et al.* (2022). The study explored the influence of instructor behavior, presence, and perceived professionalism in instructional videos. The study found that instructor enthusiasm and authenticity positively affect learners' motivation and cognitive engagement. These findings therefore reiterated the importance of humanizing video instruction to enhance learning outcomes.

On the issue of instructional videos in teaching vocational courses, Bross *et al.* (2021) conducted a meta-analysis of video modeling interventions across various educational and vocational settings. The findings

confirmed that video modeling is highly effective for teaching procedural and motor skills, especially for learners with developmental or learning disabilities. Consequently, Bakla (2022) presented a qualitative research study which examined the effectiveness of teacher-created interactive videos in blended and flipped classrooms. The study found that interactive elements, such as embedded questions and feedback, encouraged student participation and pre-class preparation. The above studies are in tandem with this research work as they gave light on how video instructions for vocational courses like OTM should be prepared.

Literature relating to the use of instructional videos for teaching higher education students was also reviewed from Chontos (2024) who reported empirical evidence supporting the use of instructor-created videos in higher education. The study reported that students perceive instructor-created videos as more relatable and motivating, leading to higher academic performance and engagement. Specifying how the video production could be done, study from Merkt et al. (2022) linked cognitive load theory to instructional video design, emphasizing the importance of segmentation and pacing to manage cognitive processing. Merkt research demonstrated that well-structured video sequences reduce extraneous load and improve procedural learning outcomes. The above studies relate to this research work as they both provide theoretical and practical guidance for optimizing multimedia instruction and as well encourage educators to produce personalized video content for better learner connection.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of teacher demonstration video on polytechnic students' achievement on Shorthand. The objectives of this study are to:

1. Ascertain the impact of teacher demonstration video on polytechnic students' achievement in Shorthand.
2. Find out the influence of gender on the achievement of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the mean achievement score of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video and those taught with conventional classroom method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video and those taught using conventional classroom method.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research adopted quasi-experimental research with a pre-test, post-test non-randomized control group design with two levels of independent variables (Teacher Demonstration video and Conventional classroom method). One level of dependent (achievement) and two level of moderating variables - gender (males and females).

The population of this study consist of all the (108) National Diploma one students of the Department of Office Technology and Management (ND1 OTM) from Abdu Gusau Polytechnic, Talata Mafara Zamfara state. The students who were in streams A and B were assigned to experimental and control groups using simple random selection technique. A sample size of 60 students obtained through the two intact classes selected from the streams above, were used for this study.

Shorthand Achievement Test (SHAT) with multiple choice items drafted out of the curriculum content taught through the video was used for data collection. The instrument was face and content validated by 2 educational technology experts from Federal College of Education [Technical], Gusau); Five (2) Shorthand lecturers from Abdu Gusau polytechnic. SHAT was pilot tested and the result which was computed using Pearson product Moment Correlation, yielded a coefficient value of (r) .79. This makes the instrument reliable. Data collected from field was used to answer the research question using mean

and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using t-test. All the analyses were conducted using SPSS version 23.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the mean achievement score of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video and those taught using conventional classroom method?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Experimental and Control Group at Pretest and Posttest

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	30	40.99	11.865	56.57	9.29	
Control	30	41.44	11.971	47.79	10.73	6.35

Source: Questionnaire administered, 2025

Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of experimental and control group at pretest and posttest. The table revealed that students in experimental group who were exposed to teacher demonstration video had mean score of 40.99 and standard deviation of 11.185 at pretest and mean score of 56.57 and standard deviation of 9.29 at posttest. The table further revealed that students in control group had mean score of 41.44 and standard deviation of 11.971 at pretest and mean score of 47.79 and standard deviation of 10.73 at posttest. The mean gain scores of 15.58 and 6.35 were recorded for experimental and control groups respectively. This means that students in the experimental group achieved greatly than those in the control group as they recorded the highest mean gain score.

Figure 1: Shows mean gain scores of experimental and control groups

Figure 1 above shows the mean gain scores between experimental and control groups at posttest. The table revealed that experimental group achieved better than the control group.

To find out the significance of the variance in the achievement scores of experimental and control groups, hypothesis one was tested.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video and conventional classroom method.

Table 2: t-test Comparison of Posttest Mean Achievement Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
Experimental	30	56.57	9.29	59	t = 3.390	.0013
Control	30	47.79	10.73			

*Significant at $p=0.05$

Table 2 above shows t-test comparison of the posttest achievement scores of students in experimental and control groups. The table revealed that calculated t-value ($t = 3.390$, $df=59$, $p<0.0013$) is significant at alpha level. Hence hypothesis one was rejected implying that significant difference exists in the Shorthand achievement score of polytechnic students exposed to teacher demonstration video and those in the control group in favour of those in the experimental group. To ascertain the magnitude of the difference which existed, Hedges' g effect size was calculated and a small effect size Cohen's $d = 0.875$ was obtained. This means, 87% of the variance occurred as a result of the influence of the experimental treatment.

Research question 2: *What are the mean achievement scores of male and female polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video?*

Table 3: Mean achievement scores of male and female polytechnic students taught shorthand using teacher demonstration video at posttest

Group	N	Post-test	
		Mean	SD
Males	18	54.39	8.67
Females	12	60.25	10.12

Source: Achievement Test Administered, 2025

The table above shows mean achievement scores of male and female polytechnic students taught shorthand using teacher demonstration video at post-test. The table revealed that female students recorded higher mean scores with 60.25 (SD 10.12), ahead of male students who obtained mean scores of 54.39 (SD, 8.67). This however shows that female students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video achieved higher than their males counterpart in the same group at post-test.

DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The research work aimed at finding the influence of teacher demonstration video on polytechnic students' achievement on Shorthand. The outcome of research question one shows the mean achievement score of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video was higher than those taught with conventional classroom method. Result of hypothesis analysis shows that a significant difference existed in the mean achievement scores of polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video and those taught using conventional classroom method with a large effect size. Consequently, the research question two reported the mean achievement scores of male and female polytechnic students taught Shorthand using teacher demonstration video. The findings revealed that female students recorded higher mean scores than their male counterparts.

The outcomes of these studies aligned with the submission of Guo *et al.* (2014) who reported that well-designed instructional videos can support procedural skill learning the result of this study is also in agreement with the findings of both Mayer, (2009) and Mrkt *et al.*, (2022) who submitted that teacher-created videos likely improved learning by increasing opportunities for observation, reducing cognitive load through segmentation, and permitting self-paced learning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the outcomes of this study, it can be concluded that:

1. Students in the experimental group (taught using teacher demonstration video) achieved significantly higher than those taught using conventional classroom method.

2. Significant difference existed between the mean achievement scores of student in the experimental group and those in the control group.
3. Female students in the experimental group achieved higher than their male counterparts in the same group.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Shorthand lecturers should critically examine the need, suitability and the possibility of attaining the instructional objectives before creating or selecting any instructional video.
2. Shorthand lecturers should use videos for instructional delivery that are not too polished to enable basic comprehension of instructional contents.
3. Shorthand lecturers should prepare instructional videos with such attributes or features that appeal to the taste of both male and female students.
3. Government, school administrators, and head of departments of relevant schools should encourage and sufficiently aid shorthand lecturers to use demonstration where necessary.

REFERENCES

- Bakla, A. (2022). Teacher-created interactive videos: Case study. *Interactive Learning Environments*.
- Beege, M., et al. (2022). How instructors influence learning with instructional videos. *Learning and Instruction*.
- Bross, L. A., et al. (2021). A meta-analysis of video modeling interventions. *Journal of Applied Behavior Analysis*.
- Chontos, A. A. (2024). Examining the impact of instructor-created videos on learning outcomes. ERIC.
- Guo, P. J., Kim, J., & Rubin, R. (2014). How video production affects student engagement. *Proceedings of the SIGCSE 2014*.
- Kay, R. H. (2012). Exploring the use of video podcasts in education: A review of the literature. *Computers & Education*, 59, 820–831.
- Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia Learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Merkt, M., et al. (2022). Cognitive load and instructional video design. *Educational Psychology Review*.
- Oden, C. (2018). *Survey into the degree of usefulness of Shorthand to modern secretaries*. Retrieved from Project Topics website: www.projecttopics.org/survey-degree-usefulness-Shorthand-modern-secretaries
- Okoro, P. E. (2018). Appraisal of students' academic performance in Shorthand in college of education, Warri. *ATBU, Journal of Science, Technology & Education (JOSTE)* , 6(2). 283-294.